

Revision of MIL-HDBK-217, Reliability Prediction of Electronic Equipment

Jeffrey W. Harms, Crane Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center

Key Words: reliability, prediction

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

This paper will discuss current efforts in the revision of MIL-HDBK-217, Military Handbook, Reliability Prediction of Electronic Equipment. It has been over a decade since this reliability prediction handbook was last updated, yet it remains the most widely used reliability prediction method for electronic equipment. In February 2008, the Defense Standardization Program Office (DSPO) tasked the Crane Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center (NSWC Crane), as the Preparing Activity, to revise MIL-HDBK-217. A plan has been created to refresh the handbook and to look at adding a new approach to better reflect reliability of electronic equipment. A working group of individuals representing Department of Defense (DoD) and industry has been established to conduct this revision. Development and implementation of solutions that reflect industry best practices and DoD needs is critical for success. Results of this task are planned to be new revisions of MIL-HDBK-217. These revisions will provide an updated reliability prediction tool that will assist reliability engineers in performing their work.

1 BACKGROUND

MIL-HDBK-217 has had a long history as a tool for use in performing reliability predictions on electronic equipment. The DoD was the first organization to put together a reliability prediction method, providing a standard means for evaluating design approaches proposed by competing contractors. Since MIL-HDBK-217 was the only reliability prediction method available at the time, the reliability community in general adopted this tool for their own use. As a result, MIL-HDBK-217 became and still is the most widely known and used reliability prediction method. There is currently an issue with the existing revision of MIL-HDBK-217. It has not been revised for over a decade and is therefore outdated. Reliability engineers from various companies are making their own modifications to MIL-HDBK-217 to achieve what it is believed to be better predictions based on their experience. However, since each organization is making their own adjustments, there is no longer consistency or standardization, which was one of the original intents of MIL-HDBK-217. This created a need to update MIL-HDBK-217 to help restore the consistency and standard way of performing reliability predictions.

NSWC Crane, as the Preparing Activity for MIL-HDBK-

217, proposed a plan to update the handbook to the DSPO. DSPO supported the idea of a MIL-HDBK-217 revision and received approval from the Systems Engineering group that “owns” MIL-HDBK-217 to proceed. In February 2008, DSPO then directed NSWC Crane to execute an update to MIL-HDBK-217.

2 REVISION APPROACH

The revision of MIL-HDBK-217 was designed as a three-phase approach to address near and long term needs. Phase 1 was established as a revision effort to refresh the data to make MIL-HDBK-217 current with today’s part technologies. The intention was to provide a relatively quick revision to MIL-HDBK-217 since the handbook was last revised in 1995.

NSWC Crane felt there was an immediate need to give the reliability community an updated handbook tool to use. The output of the Phase 1 effort will be MIL-HDBK-217 Revision G. Phases 2 and 3 go hand-in-hand and are currently planned to take a fresh look at reliability prediction, resulting in a MIL-HDBK-217 that may look much different than it does now. Phase 2 is a task that will identify a new reliability prediction methodology or approach that would determine the best way to estimate reliability of electronic equipment. Then an implementation plan will be created to determine the means for conducting the new approach. The output of Phase 2 will be a document, the Phase 2 Plan, which provides a roadmap to follow in Phase 3. The Phase 3 task is simply to execute the Phase 2 Plan. Although this sounds easy, Phase 3 will be a major task and is estimated to take a few years to complete. Phase 3 is being planned as a progressive effort that will likely result in the release of more than one revision to MIL-HDBK-217. At the time of writing this paper, MIL-HDBK-217 Revision H is planned as the first update in Phase 3.

3 PHASE DETAILS

The following describes each of the three phases in more detail.

3.1 Phase 1

The Phase 1 revision retains the existing reliability prediction methodology. The main focus was to use newer data to adjust either base failure rates or pi factors without modifying the models. Therefore the users of MIL-HDBK-

217 should experience little difficulty in adjusting to Revision G.

The sections in MIL-HDBK-217F will all remain in Revision G with one exception. Section 23 on miscellaneous parts will be deleted from the document. On the other hand, a new photonics section has been added to include part types such as multi-fiber cable assemblies, connectors, splices, isolators, transmitters, receivers, photodiodes, and others.

3.2 Phase 2

As mentioned earlier, Phase 2 will be considering a new reliability prediction approach that will likely include alternate approaches in developing reliability estimates. There are a couple main drivers associated with this direction.

The first is that parts have changed extensively since MIL-HDBK-217 was last updated in 1995. Prior to 1995, parts were designed for a long service life and from a reliability perspective, the right-end of the bathtub curve that relates to wearout was not considered. Only the flat portion in the middle of the bathtub curve relating to the use life of a part is what was determined to be important when calculating reliability predictions. MIL-HDBK-217 currently follows this mindset where the failure rate is constant and failures that occur are random failures. Today, however, the commercial industry has been driven largely by consumer electronics to produce parts that no longer compare to the parts produced prior to 1995. The parts being used currently have a shorter service life, often in the three to five year time frame. This essentially pulls in the right hand of the bathtub curve to the point where it is now necessary to pay attention to wearout as part of the reliability prediction process. As a result, Phase 2 will consider including physics of failure methods that address wearout mechanisms in parts.

The second driver is also related to how electronic parts have changed over time. Using the same time reference as above, prior to 1995 it was believed that the main driver in system failures was due to the electronic parts and this is what MIL-HDBK-217 reflects. Currently, the quality of parts being produced today is generally much better, so now the electronic parts are no longer the main cause of failures in a system. This does assume that good design practices and parts management programs are being utilized. Data collected by the Reliability Information Analysis Center (RIAC) indicates that the distribution of failure causes in a system is attributable to the following eight sources with the nominal percentage of contribution [1]: parts – 22%; no defect – 20%; manufacturing – 15%; induced – 12%; wearout – 9%; design – 9%; software – 9%; and system management – 4%. Based on this data, parts account for only 22% of system failures, meaning 78% of system failures is due to causes that are not part related. It now becomes important to pay more attention to a system level reliability prediction approach to better reflect what is happening in the field. As a result, Phase 2 will consider including a systems approach to calculating reliability estimates.

The two drivers mentioned are a major shift from the current MIL-HDBK-217 we have today and developing the

Phase 2 Plan is an important step towards creating a new reliability prediction methodology that is needed for assessing today's electronic equipment.

The next revision will also retain the existing prediction approach as a separate option for reliability engineers that want to utilize the legacy methodology.

3.3 Phase 3

The implementation of the Phase 2 Plan is what Phase 3 is all about. The Phase 2 Plan serves as the roadmap that not only captures the tasks to be performed in Phase 3, but also sets out a schedule of when the tasks will be performed. The output of Phase 3 will be a document that is a revision of MIL-HDBK-217.

4 PERFORMING THE REVISION

A MIL-HDBK-217 Working Group (217WG) was established at the beginning of the MIL-HDBK-217 revision effort to help bring ideas to the table in creating updates to the handbook and to perform the revisions. The 217WG was selected by NSWC Crane and the volunteer members represent a good cross section of individuals from industry and DoD. The members have a variety of experiences and background, which is helpful in developing the best revision possible and for gaining acceptance in the reliability community. The current members include Boeing, Honeywell, DfR Solutions, BAE Systems, Lockheed Martin, Raytheon, ManTech SRS Technologies, RIAC, ReliaSoft, Relex, Eaton, Northrop Grumman, SDA, Sandia, General Dynamics, Wright Patterson AFB, Defense Logistics Agency, and NSWC Crane.

The success of revising MIL-HDBK-217 also relies on leveraging work that has been or is being performed by other organizations in the area of reliability prediction. Revision G will likely include updated MIL-HDBK-217 pi factors determined by the VMEbus International Trade Association (VITA) industry working group in reliability (VITA 51) [2]. In Phase 3, there is a possibility for a collaborative effort with the Aerospace Vehicle Systems Institute (AVSI) to leverage their research projects. The 217WG does have a desire to coordinate with viable partners in the Phase 3 effort to achieve a reliability prediction methodology that is created and supported by the reliability community as a whole.

5 DATA

The Phase 1 revision of MIL-HDBK-217 was an effort to refresh the data to reflect today's part technologies. Acquiring the appropriate data needed to make the updates is a challenge. Usable part level data is not as readily available as it has been in the past. The 217WG was successful in capturing some data, although locating the data did take longer than anticipated. More data would be beneficial and is still being pursued for input into future revisions of MIL-HDBK-217. RIAC is being utilized to collect and sanitize the data collected from various companies. Going through RIAC allows the provider of the data to remain anonymous. The refined data is then provided to the appropriate 217WG

member for use in revising the assigned section.

In those cases where data was not available to support a change in the base failure rate or pi factors, engineering judgment was utilized. The 217WG members were only allowed to use engineering judgment if they could provide supporting information to justify a change and the 217WG agreed with the proposal.

6 SCHEDULE

The plans for the revisions of MIL-HDBK-217 are subject to change, but currently the schedule for the three phase project is as follows:

- Phase 1, Revision G draft complete – 9/25/09
- Phase 1, Revision G final version and release – 3/31/10
- Phase 2, Phase 2 Plan complete – 12/30/09
- Phase 3, Revision H draft complete – 9/30/11
- Phase 3, Revision H final version and release – 12/30/11

7 FUTURE REVISIONS

Because of the extensive changes that have taken place over time and will continue to occur in electronic part technologies, there will be a need to periodically revisit the way reliability predictions are performed for electronic equipment. Future revisions will likely include new reliability prediction methodologies. For now, the next revisions planned in Phase 3 will attempt to identify the reliability prediction methodology that is needed.

REFERENCES

1. W. Denson, *Handbook of 217Plus Reliability Prediction Models*, (May) 2006, p 146.
2. ANSI/VITA 51.1, American National Standard for Reliability Prediction, MIL-HDBK-217 Subsidiary Specification, VMEbus International Trade Association, 2008.

BIOGRAPHY

Jeffrey W. Harms
Naval Surface Warfare Center, Crane Division
Bldg 3334, Code GXMJ
300 Highway 361
Crane, Indiana 47421 USA

e-mail: jeffrey.harms@navy.mil

Jeffrey W. Harms is an electrical engineer with the Crane Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center. He has a Bachelor's Degree from Rose-Hulman Institute of Technology. While employed at NSWC Crane for the last 21 years, he has served in various positions including: component test engineer; Anti-Submarine Warfare system production support engineer; Strategic Systems Program task lead for electrical, environmental, and mechanical testing of electronic parts; reliability engineer supporting multiple DoD and industry programs; and is chairman of the MIL-HDBK-217 revision working group. He has participated in the IEEE-1413.1 and the VMEbus International Trade Association (VITA 51) reliability working groups.